

GenApp-Generated Science Gateway for Simulating Coarse-Grained Models of Linear and Torsionally Stressed Circular DNA

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Abstract—Coarse-grained (CG) modeling approaches are widely used to simulate many important biological processes involving DNA, including chromatin folding and genomic packaging. The bending propensity of a semiflexible DNA molecule critically influences these processes. Many existing CG DNA models do not retain a sufficient fidelity of the important local chain motions, whose propagation at larger length scales would generate correct DNA persistent lengths, in particular, when the solution’s ionic strength is widely varied. We have recently developed an accurate CG model for double-stranded DNA which generates values for the persistence length in a wide range of NaCl concentrations, in near quantitative agreement with numerous experimental measurements. The model also predicts the structural transition of torsionally stressed DNA nanocircles as the salt concentration is varied, a mechanism suggested to regulate genome organization and regulation. Our CG dsDNA model is intended for use with the Large-scale Atomic/Molecular Massively Parallel Simulator (LAMMPS), an open-source Molecular Dynamics (MD) engine. Since our model is currently not a part of an official LAMMPS distribution, there is a significant learning curve for a potential user to utilize our model, including LAMMPS compilation with our custom CG interaction potentials, as well as a proper definition of our model in the LAMMPS input files. The problem is compounded by the further complexity of compiling our in-house developed packages relying on specialized libraries facilitating with building initial CG DNA structures, especially DNA nanocircles possessing arbitrary torsional stress. In addition, use of these disparate command-line applications require users to set up the run time environment and also to possess some Bash programming skills. All these difficulties inevitably limits accessibility of our CG model to a broader simulation community. Here we present a science gateway for automated building, parametrizing, and simulating linear and circular DNA systems using our CG model. To rapidly deploy our science gateway, we utilized Generalized Application generation framework (GenApp, <https://genapp.rocks>) designed to tremendously simplify creation of web-based applications. With the most work on the actual deployment performed by a high-school student, we will share an experience of a non-computer science expert incorporating our CG DNA and required structure building tools into GenApp and illustrate the use of the gateway.

Index Terms—GenApp, Generalized Application Framework, Science Gateway, MD Simulations, DNA Nanocircles, Coarse-Graining

I. INTRODUCTION

Many exciting biological processes involving DNA occur over time- and length-scales that are not amenable to computational modeling using refined all-atom (AA) molecular dynamics (MD) simulations. To model these complex biological systems, coarse-grained (CG) representations of the DNA are required that would be simple enough to permit exhaustive simulations in a reasonable amount of time, yet complex enough to capture the essential physics at play. For example, to address the million-fold compaction of DNA into a highly organized structure called chromatin [1], [2], one needs to deal with dozens of nucleosomal core particles connected by linker DNA chains. Each nucleosome core particle is a nucleoprotein complex, with ~ 150 DNA basepairs wrapped around a protein histone core of ~ 1200 residues. Because of the enormous number of atoms in even the shortest AA representation of the chromatin fiber segments, a simplified CG representation is required for meaningful computational modeling.

CG modeling can be viewed as a clever way of separating and disregarding irrelevant atomistic noise from the subset of degrees of freedom which facilitate the sampling of the more interesting long timescale behavior. For example, when developed from AA MD simulations, coarse graining implies “integrating out” microscopic fluctuations coming from the solvent (lion’s share of all degrees of freedom in a typical AA system), as well as the irrelevant DNA degrees of freedom (depends on a desired CG system resolution).

One of the key difficulties specific to the DNA coarse graining is the correct handling of electrostatics forces, which are rather complex near highly charged DNA, and where many-body effects of the ionic environment need to be properly taken into account [3]. In particular, the response of the DNA persistence length to the change in the surrounding ionic environment is of major biological importance; even a slight change in the persistence length of a linker DNA segment connecting adjacent nucleosomes in the chromatin fiber, induced by the variation of the ionic strength of the

Fig. 1. CG model for the DNA chain in the NaCl salt buffer is shown [4]. Each DNA base pair is represented by 2 beads, each placed in the geometric center of the corresponding atomistic nucleotide. Blue dashed lines indicate the “fan” interactions which represent a superposition of stacking and base pairing among two polynucleotides.

solution, may result in significant conformational changes of a chromatin in a compact state.

Recently, we systematically derived a 2-bead per base pair model of double-stranded (ds) DNA with explicit mobile ions by matching CG and detailed atomistic partition functions (Fig. 1) [4]–[6]. The resulting CG model of a dsDNA chain generated a fluctuation spectrum of complex local motions that was shown to be highly similar to what was observed in AA MD simulations with explicit solvent, ions, and detailed representation of DNA. Furthermore, propagation of these local motions also allows for a correct description of large-scale DNA behavior (Fig. 2A) [7]. In addition, the model was recently used to study the conformational behavior of DNA interacting with a charged sphere, subject to an external stretching force exerted on the ends of DNA chain, mimicking the unwrapping of the nucleosome (Fig. 2B) [8]–[10]. Another important application of the model was the prediction of structural phase transitions in torsionally stressed DNA nanocircles caused by variation of the salt concentration (Fig. 2C) [4]. This computational study has an important biological implication in nucleosomal assembly, where torsional stress may be present, and a delicate balance between DNA elastic and electrostatic effects may regulate nucleosomal stability [11]–[13].

Our CG dsDNA model is intended for use with the Large-scale Atomic/Molecular Massively Parallel Simulator (LAMMPS) [14], an open-source MD simulation engine whose code-base allows for a relatively easy implementation of arbitrary, user-defined functional forms for inter-particle interaction potentials. Since our model is currently not a part of an official LAMMPS distribution, there is a significant learning curve for a potential user to utilize our model, including LAMMPS compilation with our custom-defined interaction potentials, as well as proper definition of our model in several LAMMPS input files. The problem is compounded by further complexity of building more sophisticated (than linear) DNA structures, such as circular DNA fragments possessing arbitrary torsional stress (relaxed, or under/overwound). Our in-house, command-line applications to generate

Fig. 2. Recent applications of our CG DNA model. (A) The model was used to measure DNA persistence length in a wide range of NaCl concentrations, covering three order of magnitudes; computational results appeared to be in quantitative agreement with experimental data [7]. (B) The model was employed in a study of the behavior of DNA-nanosphere complex mimicking nucleosome core particle [8]; typical MD simulation snapshots demonstrate nucleosomal wrapping. (C) The model predicts a pronounced phase transition to a buckled state in the over-twisted 90-base-pair DNA nano-circle at physiological concentrations of NaCl salt buffer [4].

initial CG DNA structures rely on use of the Biochemical Algorithms Library (BALL) [15]; compilation of BALL (not a straightforward operation), setting run time environment, generating DNA initial structures and LAMMPS input files, as well as using LAMMPS in a command-line or script-based mode inevitably limit accessibility of our CG DNA model to a broader scientific community. To address this deficiency, we used GenApp-based technology [16] to transform all these tools, libraries, and packages into a unified science gateway.

number of helical repeats is “removed” from the originally relaxed DNA circle, resulting in even a looser overall structure.

2) *Simulation Parameters*: LAMMPS MD simulations are configured by quite a limited set of parameters: temperature (K), time of the ionic equilibration (number of steps), and the time of productive MD simulations (number of steps). The first time defines the longevity of the equilibration period where only surrounding ions are allowed to move, while DNA molecule is constrained. Since system equilibration is highly desirable, the lower limit is set to 10,000 steps. During productive run all particles are allowed to move. Other relevant parameters are preset as required by our CG model. For example, the upper limit of the simulation timestep (10 fs) which can be used to simulate CG systems without any instabilities was determined based on the criteria of the total energy conservation; next, the canonical NVT integration scheme was the only reasonable ensemble for (generally speaking any) CG simulations with no explicit solvent [4].

3) *Mode of Computing*: User can choose to simulate using serial or MPI LAMMPS binary. In the latter case, a number of processors should be specified (from 2 to 16 CPUs).

4) *Output Section*: Live output fields start to be populated immediately after clicking the “Submit” button. These include the live output from the LAMMPS execution (textarea), and visualization of the simulation progress (progress bar and percentage). Other output fields represent links to the produced files: (1) .PDB file of the generated initial CG structure and input LAMMPS files (“LAMMPS Input Files”); (2) .DCD files of equilibration and productive simulations (“Simulation Trajectory”); and (3) combined simulation log file. In addition to output of generated CG system’s coordinates in the form downloadable .PDB and .DCD files, our science gateway also allows users to immediately visualize the resulting 3D structures using integrated biomolecular visualization tool JSmol [17].

C. Future Improvements

Currently, the gateway is hosted on a 16 core VM on NSF Jetstream2 [18]. This will pose limitations in future, when larger CG systems and simulation times are at play. We will address this by extending the gateway to support elastic cloud computing [19]. Another planned improvement is proper user management and statistics including GenApp’s inherent login/registration and OAuth2 and Globus Connect based user credential management. Finally, we plan to create a unified science gateway that combines the currently described CG DNA creator and simulator with additional simulation trajectory analysis tools.

III. CONCLUSIONS

We used GenApp to combine our disparate command-line programs and scripts into a unified web-application, to build initial CG structures of linear and torsionally stressed DNA fragments, generate system’s topology, parameter, and input files for subsequent serial and MPI LAMMPS MD simulations. Such automation and ease of use makes our CG DNA

model accessible to a broader computational community. Our experience demonstrated that GenApp, designed to simplify creation and deployment of web-based applications over a collection of modules, turned out to be a suitable and intuitive tool for a high school student (MS) who successfully deployed the gateway presented in this paper.

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